

Strength of Epoxy Resin under Multiaxial Stress Field

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ABSTRACT

The strength of epoxy resin under multiaxial stress field is investigated and discussed on the basis of the experimental data. With respect to the fracture mechanism of the epoxy resin, a maximum principal-strain theory is proposed on the basis of the consideration that fracture initiates essentially by the break of polymer chain which may have a limit of extensibility. The effect of the defect part in the polymer solid such as holes and small impurity contents of rigid particle effects on the strength. An attempt to estimate the multiaxial strength of Epoxy resin is made on the basis of strength of polymer chain and good agreement between the fracture criteria obtained by the estimation and the experiment is obtained.

INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resin is a three-dimensional cross-linked polymer and one of the polymer used widely for matrix material of fiber reinforced composites. In the composite, the resin is subjected multi-axial stress and strain states in general and it is necessary to know the strength of this polymer under these multi-axial stress field in order to interpret the strength of the composite. In this presentation, the strength of the epoxy resin under biaxial stress field is mainly discussed on the basis of experimental results, a part of these result has been reported by the author at the 2'nd international conference on mechanical behavior of materials in 1976. In this time in 1976, only phenomenological treatment of experimental data was reported and a fracture criterion in which the two criteria, the maximum principal stress theory and the internal friction theory are combined. In this presentation, the maximum strain theory is examined to interpret the experimental results on the basis of a network model of polymer chains.

EXPERIMENTAL

Testing Method

The epoxy resin used in this experiment is Epikote 828 and its curing condition is shown in Table 1. The complex dynamic modulus of this resin at 10Hz is shown in Fig.1 with that property of unsaturated polyester resin "Polylite" which is also a cross-linked thermosets and used as a reference material in this research. Experiment is carried out in room temperature condition, $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. Five testing methods are used in order to obtain various biaxial stress states as followings.

- (1) Simultaneous shearing-tension testing of a strip plate(Fig.2).
- (2) Burst of a spherical thin shell by hydrostatic pressure(Fig.3). The strain is measured by a strain gauge put on the top of spherical shell and the stress by the pressure inside of the shell by equation: $\sigma = P \cdot R / 2H$, where P;pressure,R;inner radius and H;thickness of shell. Only equal biaxial stress field can be obtained by this method. Specimen of various size are tested to inspect their size effect on the biaxial strength.
- (3) Simultaneous twisting and compression testing of a thin tube(Fig.4). A cylinder tube having a thin part as shown in Fig.4 is used for this testing and the thick part of tube are cramped and the twisting and compression are applied through this thick part. This method is used for obtaining the data for the second quadrant of the principal stress domain.
- (4) Uniaxial compression of a rod.
- (5) Uniaxial extension. Specimen of various size are tested to inspect the size effect on the strength.
- (6) "porker chip" method (Fig.5). As a trial of triaxial stress-field testing, this method is examined. A thin plate is fixed between two steel plates by adhesion as shown in Fig.5. A external load is applied in the direction perpendicular to the plate face, where the strain in the direction perpendicular to the load is kept nearly zero. This method induces a triaxial stress state.

Biaxial Strength

The principal stresses to break this epoxy resin under biaxial stress field are shown in Fig.6. The lines drawn in this figure are the criterion shown by following equations(1).

$$\sigma_m \geq \sigma_b \quad (1), \quad \tau_m \geq \tau_b - \mu \sigma \quad (2)$$

This equations show that the resin will break either the maximum principal stress σ_m attains at a critical stress σ_b ($= 70 \text{ MNm}^{-2}$) or the maximum shear stress τ_m at the condition (2) where τ_b , μ and σ are the critical shear stress, frictional coefficient and normal stress component acting on the slipping plane respectively. From the experiment, these values are: $\sigma_b = 70 \text{ MNm}^{-2}$, $\tau_b = 70.7 \text{ MNm}^{-2}$, $\mu = 0.601$. This criterion, however, has been obtained only by curve fitting based on two observed facts, the fracture surface obtained by the simultaneous shear and tension testing is perpendicular to the maximum normal stress as shown in Fig.7, and the fact that the direction of the fracture surface of the broken pieces caused by uniaxial compression testing inclines about 45 degree against the compression direction. This suggests a fracture caused by shear stress(Fig.8).

Importance of the Defects in Polymer solid

Beside these biaxial and uniaxial testings, the effect of specimen size on strength of the resin was also examined. Fig.9 shows the dependence of uniaxial tensile strength on sample size. The similar result was also obtained from equal biaxial stress state obtained by the spherical shell of various size as shown in Fig.10. Fig.11 is the fracture surface of the epoxy resin caused by uniaxial extension of a thin rod specimen of which diameter is 0.5mm. Because of the small surface, inspection of the fracture surface is easy. As seen in this picture, a defect point is observed. This type of defect is observed at every experiment repeated without exception. These results suggest us a possibility that any defect plays an important role at fracture initiation.

A FRACTURE CRITERION BASED ON AN IMPERFECT BODY

If polymer chains of the epoxy resin is straightened and all of these chains can effectively support internal force of the resin, the estimated Young's modulus of the bulk polymer is calculated as follows. Consider a cubic inside of body as shown in Fig.12 and that the straightened polymer chains penetrate into this cubic at random and also assume that the chains are fixed their ends at the surface of the cubic(affine deformation assumption). When the cubic is deformed along three axes X_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) by stretch ratios λ_i , then the sum of the normal-force component of each of the chains at i th surface, t_i is given by:

$$\bar{t}_3 = \text{ESN} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi \int_0^{\pi/2} \{\lambda_3(1-1/B)\cos\theta\} f(\theta, \phi) \sin\theta \cos\theta \, d\theta \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\bar{t}_2 = \text{ESN} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi \int_0^{\pi/2} \lambda_2(1-1/B) f(\theta, \phi) \sin^3\theta \sin^2\phi \, d\theta \quad \dots(4)$$

$$\bar{t}_1 = \text{ESN} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi \int_0^{\pi/2} \lambda_1(1-1/B) f(\theta, \phi) \sin^3\theta \cos^2\phi \, d\theta \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\text{where } B = \{(\lambda_1 \sin\theta \cos\phi)^2 + (\lambda_2 \sin\theta \sin\phi)^2 + (\lambda_3 \cos\theta)^2\}^{1/2} \quad \dots(6)$$

$f(\theta, \phi)$; probability density function of the chains along θ, ϕ direction

X_i ; stretch ratio along X_i axes ($i=1,2,3$)

ES ; tensile stiffness of a chain

N ; effective number of chains and equal to the (total length of the chains in the cubic)/(length of an edge of cubic)

If the isotropic orientation of random chains is assumed, then $f(\theta, \phi) = 1/4\pi$ ($0 < \phi < 2\pi, 0 < \theta < \pi$). Considering the deformation $\lambda_3 > 1, \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 1$, and also small deformation, followings are obtained:

$$\bar{t}_3 = \frac{\text{ESN}}{5} (\lambda_3 - 1), \quad \bar{t}_2 = \bar{t}_1 = \frac{\text{ESN}}{15} (\lambda_3 - 1)$$

and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.25$, Bulk modulus $E = (1/6)\text{ESN}$

Substituting the appropriate values of ES and N for EPIKOTE 828, following results are obtained ;

$$E_{\text{cal}} = 2.3 \times 10^4 \text{ MNm}^{-2}, \quad \nu = 0.25$$

The observed values at 20°C are ;

$$E_{\text{obs}} = 3.09 \times 10^3 \text{ MNm}^{-2}, \quad \nu = 0.25$$

The ratio $E_{\text{obs}}/E_{\text{cal}}$ is about 8. Roughly the number of effective chains supporting the internal force is assumed to be 1/8 of ideal value of N. The strength of uniaxially oriented chains of EPIKOTE is estimated to be $1.5 \times 10^4 \text{ kg/cm}^2$. Considering the effective number of chains supporting the force, the estimated strength of the resin is ;

$$\sigma_B = 1.5 \times 10^3 \cdot (1/8) = 1.9 \times 10^2 \text{ MNm}^{-2} = 2 \sim 3 \times \sigma_B \text{ (observed)}$$

Here, the assumption is made regarding the fracture such that if the principal strain of the bulk polymer attains the critical value, the fracture will initiate. This criterion is based on the assumption of the maximum extensibility of polymer chains. The finite element analysis on the strain distribution around a hole or around a small particle of rigid body inside of the body shows that the strain which is about 2~3 times of bulk strain. Considering these effects, it is obtained that the estimated value of strength is nearly equal to the observed value. The criterion on the basis of this defect theory and the maximum principal strain theory is shown in Fig. 13 and good agreement between prediction and observation is obtained qualitatively and also quantitatively.

Triaxial Stress Field

The strength is about the same level as those of uniaxial strength. This experiment is still carried on.

CONCLUSION

A fracture criterion based on the chain network model has been presented. In this estimation, an assumption is made such that the maximum strain around the defects inside the body initiate fracture. The theory presented here is so simple and the effect of intermolecular forces has been ignored in this theory, however, the fracture criterion on the basis of the network model well

estimate the experimental results. The more experimental surveys for the strength of the other type of cross-linked polymers is necessary to find more details of the fracture mechanism.

REFERENCES

- 1) S.KAWABATA et.al. ; Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Mechanical Behavior of Materials, August 1976, Boston, USA, American Society for Metals

Table 1

Epoxy resin	EPIKOTE 828	100
Hardner	$C_2H_5NH_2 \cdot BF_3$	3 phr
Curing	120 °C	3hr
After cure	180 °C	1hr

Fig 1 Complex dynamic modulus of specimen

$$\sigma_{22} = \nu \sigma_{11}$$

$$\sigma_1, \sigma_2 = \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22}) \pm \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + 4\sigma_{12}^2}$$

Fig.2 Simultaneous shear/tension testing.

$$\sigma = \frac{PR}{2H}$$

P : pressure
R : radius
H : thickness

Fig.3 Burst testing of a thin spherical shell by water pressure.

Fig.4 Simultaneous twisting/torsion testing.

Fig.5 "Porker chip" method for triaxial strength test. This testing is continuing now.

Fig.6 Biaxial strength and fracture criterion presented before.

Fig.7 Fracture surface is perpendicular to the maximum principal stress.

Fig.8 Fracture caused by uniaxial compression.

Fig.9 Effect of specimen size on strength/uniaxial.

Fig.10 Effect of specimen size on strength/equal biaxial.

Fig.11 A defect is found on fracture surface/thin rod specimen of 0.5mm dia.

Fig.12 A random network model.

Fig.13 Biaxial strength and fracture criterion on the basis of maximum principal strain with effect of defect part.